

Apêndice B - Ferramentas de pesquisa e limitadores aplicados em cada um das bases de dados

Bases de dados	Limitadores
Scopus	(LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA, "SOC")) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "Spanish")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SRCTYPE, "j")) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBSTAGE, "final"))
EBSCO (AcademicSearch Complete)	Limitadores: Texto Integral; Revistas Científicas (Analisadas pelos Pares); Data de Publicação: 20130101-20231231 Restringir por Language: spanish Restringir por Language: english Modos de pesquisa - Booleana/Frase
EBSCO (Eric)	Limitadores - Analisado pelos Pares; Data de Publicação: 20130101-20231231; PublicationType: AcademicJournal Restringir por Language: english Modos de pesquisa - Booleana/Frase
Web ofScience (SciELO)	Publication year 2013 or 2015 or 2016 or 2017 or 2018 or 2019 or 2020 or 2021 or 2022 or 2023 Document Types: Research Article SciELO Categories: Social Sciences Interdisciplinary or Education Educational research. Languages: Spanish or English or Portuguese. Research areas: Education Educational Research or Social Sciences Other Topics or Psychology
Web of Science (Core Collection)	Document Types: Article. Web of Science Categories: Education Educational Research or Psychology Multidisciplinary or Physiology or Social Sciences Interdisciplinary

	<p>Web of Science Index: Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) or Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI).</p> <p>Languages: English or Spanish</p>
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Fonte: Dados da pesquisa